

THE NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY

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ELSEVIER

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Annotatsiya: The article covers the need and importance of the transition to a green economy, the structure of the green economy and its important peculiarities, its importance in the development of countries, ensuring the stability of economic growth. The production of renewable energy sources has been addressed in detail to the issues of reducing carbon emissions, ensuring energy savings.

Kalit so'zlar: green economy, carbon monoxide, energy conservation, energy density, environmental change, climate change, green finance.

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In world practice, special importance is attached to the study of sustainable development of territories, their economic and environmental systems in their effective harmony. In particular, the development of countries directly depends on the stability of the regions, and the positive aspects of this issue include the rational and effective use of resources based on the expansion of the innovative economy. In particular, the correct Organization of production activities in the economy, ensuring the duration and growth of the industry depends on the availability of resources. This is due to the effective implementation of management decisions aimed at ensuring the harmony of economic and environmental systems in ensuring the stability of the regions.

Production of renewable energy sources reducing carbon emissions SO₂, increasing green-tech greenhouses, water recycling and delivery based on green technologies, "green" transport tools, car electrification, "green" households, production of clean environmental products in cities, production of environmentally friendly, organic food in agriculture are important today.

The formation of a "green" economy and the transition to its sustainable development are priorities both at the global level and for Uzbekistan. The concept of sustainable development is an important resource for the future of mankind, which is embodied in the decisions and documents of the UN. The economic and environmental basis of sustainable development is the formation and development of this "green" economy. To overcome current unstable trends, in 2015, specific UN

criteria for the development of 17 "green" economies for the period up to 2030 were identified.

The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 2, 2022, PQ-436 "on measures to improve the efficiency of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy by 2030" established the goals of transition to the green economy of Uzbekistan. According to this decision 2022 – Implementation of the tasks set out in the new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2026, increasing the efficiency of measures implemented to ensure green and inclusive economic growth within the framework of the transition strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy, the use of renewable energy and further expansion of resource savings in all sectors of the economy, the program "transition to a green economy and Also, the goal was to reduce greenhouse gases by 35% compared to the level of previous years, increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources to 15 gvt, significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy. To reduce the volume of energy per unit of gross domestic product by 30% (compared to 2021), reduce electricity consumption in the industry, share in total consumption by 20%, expand the share of renewable energy resources in the total volume of electricity production by 30.5% (including hydropower) in order to ensure the transition to a "green" economy and, Within the framework of the "green space" project, indicators were set for the expansion of green spaces in cities by 30% (in relation to the total area of the settlement).

In the next decade, the "green economy" had a significant impact in improving the folk lifestyle, increasing their Real income. But the "green economy" has not fully formed and developed, its level of influence is currently limited, it is not able to fully satisfy the growing and expanding people's preferences in conditions of resource shortages, therefore it has not become the basis of socio-economic, sustainable development of society.

The issues of the need for a green economy, its peculiarities, transition to a "green" economy in industrial sectors, ensuring energy efficiency are part of the process of reforming the economy of Uzbekistan and occupy a special place in the country's economy in protecting the environment, ensuring sustainable development. Today, achieving the goals for "green progress" is one of the urgent tasks.

Green economy refers to a new direction of economic activity based on the implementation of the further development of the economy associated with the production and service sectors, while maintaining the resources necessary for human life and health, the environment and ecology as a whole.

The concept of green economics emerged at the end of the 20th century, emphasizing the need to reduce the negative impact of human economic activity on

the environment in economics. A trend that in any case focuses not on economic growth, but on Sustainable Development. environment. Proponents of this trend believe that the economy is a dependent component of the natural environment in which it exists and is part of it.

Including M.A. In his research, Gureeva cited a number of problems in the development of a "green" economy, citing as their solutions the introduction of fines for negatively affecting the environment; reduction of the release of toxic substances; the need to introduce the practice of restoring damage to the environment. The implementation of these measures will lead to an increase in the well-being and quality of living of the population. The green economy helps people to use pure environmental services and products.

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